

Review

Characteristics and influencing factors of gas explosion propagation in pipelines (ducts) – A review

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Abstract: In an attempt to satisfy the energy demand in a world with depleting levels of fossil-fuels, coal exploitation will remain even though attempts to reduce CO₂ emission is discussed across the length and breadth of the world and with the increasing depths in countries like China and Australia the direct challenge of catastrophic explosions are inevitable. Similarly, municipal sewage system and urban public infrastructure are a ticking time bomb if oil and gas leakages are taken into consideration. With these scenarios research have discovered that, a number of characteristic factors including obstacles, vents, bends, ignition features, explosion/flammable limits, fuel concentration, gas concentration and composition, overpressure etc., influence the flame propagation that bring about gas explosions in pipelines. Understanding these influencing factors provide comprehensive ways of mitigating the gas explosion in pipeline (ducts). From various researches a considerable number of suppression, venting and isolation technologies have been discovered to mitigate the gas explosion in ducts. Examples of such discoveries include the use of water mist and its derivatives, ultrafine water fog, side/size/end venting and porous solids.

Keywords: Gas explosion, Obstacle, Flammability limits, Pipelines (ducts), Venting

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Introduction

The foreseeable depletion of fossil-fuels and the observable deterioration of natural-environment have prompted scholars to conduct extensive research on efficient and clean energy^[1]. To address the energy demand, coal exploitation has extended to increasing depths^[2] even though it is acknowledged to be the primary source of CO₂ emission. The increased depth of coal exploitation has increased the number of gas outbursts drastically and with excessive gas stimulation occurring at times. When combined with the incidence of sparks produced by the friction of coal cutters, tunnel boring

machines, conveyor belts, etc., gas explosions are more likely to occur^[3]. Generally, the expanded application of coal gas, natural gas and LPG (Liquefied Petroleum Gas) in all fields makes it urgent and imperative to prevent combustible gas explosion disasters in such engineering projects^[4]. As an essential part of urban public infrastructure, municipal sewage pipelines are highly vulnerable to gas explosion accidents leading to heavy casualties, property and huge economic losses and negative impact on society^[5] because flammable gases often accumulate due to the massive scale of the sewer system, its numerous branches, and its airtightness^[6]. A number of underground explosions have occurred throughout the world. The worst underground mining tragedy, caused by a gas explosion in Australia, killed 96 people in 1902^[7]. In 1942 the deadliest underground coal mine explosion in human history occurred at the Benxihu Colliery in China resulting in 1549 fatalities^[8]. On July 31, 2014, a series of gas explosions from an underground pipeline occurred in Kaohsiung, Taiwan, causing 32 fatalities and 321 injuries^[9]. A volatile oil-gas mixture accumulated within a closed municipal sewage conduit exploded because of a spark during the Sinopec Donghuang underground oil pipeline leakage and the explosion accident in Qingdao, Shandong Province, China, on November 22, 2013. This accident resulted in 63 deaths, 156 injuries, and a direct economic loss of nearly RMB 752 million^[5, 6]. Owing to what such disastrous consequences the gas explosions pose to the production safety of coal mines and public safety have necessitated numerous research on how to effectively and reliably isolate gas explosion flame and shock wave propagation in order to mitigate the losses subsequent to gas explosion disasters in underground or confined spaces^[5, 10]. In an experiment Zhai et al., studied the propagation of gas explosion within a bent pipeline and found that, the explosion and flame propagation velocity rose sharply at the bend due to the interaction between the pressure wave and flame^[11]. Kundu, et al., found that the presence of turbulence increased the peak overpressure of gas explosions in a confined spherical chamber^[12]. Lin et al.^[13] and Yu et al.^[4], experimentally investigated the influence of obstacles on flame propagation speed. They found that the obstacles exerted significant influence on the flame and explosive wave propagating in the duct. To reduce the great losses caused by gas explosions in the gas transportation process and to improve the explosion venting efficiency in pipelines, Yu et al.^[14], developed a small pipeline with both a side vent and an end vent, and premixed methane/air explosion characteristics were studied in the pipeline with different side venting areas. The experimental results indicated that in the same side venting position, with an increasing venting area, the propagation time for flames through the pipeline increases on a large scale, the peak overpressure of the methane explosion drops significantly, and the venting effect is greatly enhanced. To better understand and to remedy the fatal consequences of gas explosion Wen et al.^[15], studied the combined effects of obstacle and fine water mist on gas explosion characteristic. They realized that, the inhibitory effect of 45 μm water veils of mist on gas explosion weakened firstly and then enhanced with the increasing distance between obstacle location from the ignition location as well as in several obstacles.

Li et al.^[16], conducted a numerical analysis of the characteristics of gas explosion process in natural gas compartment of utility tunnel (as shown in **Fig. 1-1**: the urban utility tunnels normally contain electricity pipelines, natural gas pipelines, heat pipelines, sewer pipelines, etc.) using FLACS. The results revealed that the flame profile undergoes two unstable flame stages. When the ignition position is set at the middle area (100.25, 1.2, 1.4 m) of the 200 m-long natural gas compartment, the maximum overpressure of the gas explosion in the 200 m-long natural gas compartment is 25.17 bar, which is the largest maximum overpressure under all gas explosion simulation setups.

Fig. 1-1 The internal structure of an urban underground utility tunnel^[16]

This review is primarily aimed at enumerating the characteristics and influencing factors that affect gas explosion propagation in pipelines (ducts). Therefore, Chapter 2 will discuss in brief detail some influencing factors and their impact on gas explosion propagation while Chapter 3 briefly outline some innovative approaches and models that have assisted in mitigating the inevitable gas explosions in the world’s quest to provide energy, conceal sewage system, transport and store gases over distances, etc

2 Gas Explosion Phenomenon and Characteristic Influencing Factors

2.1 Gas Explosion Phenomenon

Gas explosion can be defined as a process where combustion of a premixed gas cloud, i.e. fuel-air or fuel/oxidizer is causing rapid increase of pressure. Gas explosions can occur inside process equipment or pipes, in buildings or offshore modules, in open process areas or in unconfined areas. Gas explosion can be referred to as an event in a more general sense and may feature events both before and after the gas explosion process as shown in Fig. 2-1^[17].

Fig. 2-1 An event tree showing typical consequences of accidental release of combustible gas or evaporating liquid into the atmosphere^[17]

Fig 2-1 depicts the likelihood and chain of events when a combustible gas or evaporating liquid is accidentally released into process equipment or pipes, in buildings or offshore modules. If the gas cloud, formed from the release, is not within the flammability limits or if an ignition source is lacking, the gas cloud may be diluted and eventually disappear. Ignition may occur immediately, or may be delayed by up to tens of minutes, all depending on the circumstances. In case of an immediate ignition (i.e. before mixing with air or oxidizer has occurred) a fire will occur^[17]. It is very catastrophic in instances where large combustible premixed fuel-air cloud is formed and ignites. The consequences of a gas explosion will depend on the environment in which the gas cloud is contained or which the gas cloud engulfs. Therefore it has been common to classify a gas explosion from the environment where the explosion takes place: i) Confined Gas Explosions within vessels, pipes, channels or tunnels. ii) Partly Confined Gas Explosions in a compartment, buildings or off-shore modules and iii) Unconfined Gas Explosions in process plants and other unconfined areas. Due to the review topic, the classification will be restricted to confined gas explosions^[17].

2.1.1 Confined Gas explosions

Confined gas explosions are explosions within tanks (as shown in **Fig. 2-2**), process equipment, pipes, in culverts, sewage systems, closed rooms and in underground installations. Confined explosions are also referred to as internal explosions.

Fig. 2-2 Confined explosion within a tank (Modified from^[17])

2.1.2 Deflagration and Detonation

In gas explosions, deflagration is the most common form of flame propagation, and is defined as the flame front that propagates at subsonic velocities. The deflagration can transform to a detonation if the deflagration becomes sufficiently strong^[17]. When a cloud is ignited the flame can propagate in two different modes through the flammable parts of the cloud. These modes are:

- (i) Deflagration
- (ii) Detonation

Deflagration

The deflagration mode of flame propagation is the most common. A deflagration propagates at subsonic speed relative to the unburnt gas, typical flame speeds (i.e. relative to a stationary observer) are of the order of 1-1000 ms⁻¹. The explosion pressure may reach values of several bar, depending on the flame speed^[17].

Detonation

A detonation wave is a supersonic (relative to the speed of sound in the unburnt gas ahead of the wave) combustion wave. The shock wave and the combustion wave are in this case coupled. In a fuel-air cloud a detonation wave will propagate at a velocity of 1500-2000 ms⁻¹ and the peak pressure is typically 15-20 bar^[17].

2.2 Characteristics and influencing factors of gas explosion propagation in pipelines (ducts)

The severity of gas explosion is influenced by the presence of a number of factors, such as obstacles^[18], vent conditions^[19], geometry shape, turbulent behavior, ignition features^[20, 21], flammability limits of combustible gas mixtures etc^[22]. Traditionally, these influencing factors may extensively affect the propagation of gas explosion, and may lead to “deflagration to detonation transition” (DDT)^[23].

2.2.1 Obstacles

With the wide use of natural gas, gas explosion accidents often occur unexpectedly, causing casualties and property loss. When they occur, they can meet obstacles which are unavoidable in flammable gas storage and transportation systems. Many research works^[24, 25] have focused on the effect of obstacles on gas explosion: some focused on a simple single-obstacle, such as spiral obstacles^[26, 27], a flat obstacles, circular obstacles^[28] etc.

Due to the presence of obstacles in a gas explosion process the flow becomes non-uniform and that can make the turbulence of the flow the consequence of the gas explosion. It is worth nothing that, the shape, blockage ratio and the separation distances of obstacles influence gas explosion propagation to a grave extent. Lin et al.^[29], investigated the influence of obstacle on methane-air mixture explosion with respect to flame and explosion wave and found that obstacles intensify the turbulence phenomenon in the process of flame propagation.

Influence of the shape of obstacle on Gas Explosion

Different kinds of geometries of obstacles such as circular, square, rectangular, triangular, cylindrical and diamond have been employed to investigate and evaluate the influence of obstacle shape on flame shape^[30, 31], pressure^[30], velocity^[32, 33] etc., on the propensity of gas explosion propagation in pipelines. Xiao et al.^[34], analyzed the effect of obstacle shape on gas explosion characteristics by conducting an experimental studies of flame propagation behavior influenced by quadrangular, cylindrical, and triangular obstacles using a 530 mm × 82 mm × 82 mm pipe. The results confirm the understanding that obstacles with a tip promote the generation of flow instability and produce a more intense burning behavior of the flame. In triangular obstacles, the shear layer become prominent in the later stage of the explosion process and this contributes to enhancing the flame velocity and overpressure. The effect of the quadrangular obstacles on flame velocity is mainly influenced by gas flow at the flame front. In the flame propagation process, the quadrangular obstacles have a more obvious promoting effect of the initial explosion, but the degree is weaker than with the triangular obstacles^[34].

Influence of Blockage Ratio on Gas Explosion

Circcarelli et al.^[28], reported that, the flame velocity reaches a maximum when the interval of obstacles is equal to the diameter of the tube under high blockage ratios after experimentally studying the effect of circular obstacles on flame acceleration. In a different experiment Johansen and Circcarelli^[18], investigated the effect of the obstacle blockage ratio on flame propagation and found that the initial rates of flame acceleration were higher for large blockage ratios and can accelerate flame velocity close to the product of the speed of sound. Yu et al.^[35], also reported that, when an obstacle blockage ratios are the same, the final flame velocity has nothing to do with shape and spacing of obstacles, spacing of which only affects the rate of flame acceleration.

2.2.2 Explosion/Flammable Limits

The flammability limit (also referred to as the explosion limit) is a key parameter used to evaluate the combustion characteristics and explosion risk of flammable gas mixtures. A flammability limit can simply be defined as a concentration limit beyond which a flame will not propagate^[36, 37]. Wang et al.^[38], reported that, the flammability limit of gas has a volume effect. They found out that, the flammability limit for pure methane in an elongated pipeline with the volume of 76 dm³ is 9%-17%. The increase of the flammability limit range under the condition of gas-liquid coexistence increases the risk of gas explosion, and this increase in explosion risk can be analyzed and explained from restricted

space and the triple desk theory of the boundary layer. In standard experiments, the LFL of methane explosion is generally between 4% and 6%, and the UFL of methane explosion is generally between 15% and 17%^[39]. The flammability limit is not an independent parameter, which is affected by the initial temperature, pressure, limited space and other factors^[40].

2.2.3 Vent Conditions

To study the influence on the methane/air explosion characteristics of the side venting position in a pipeline Yu et al.^[41], employed a small size square pipeline to simulate natural gas explosions in a pipeline. By installing side vents at different positions, the characteristics of the methane explosion under different side venting positions were studied. They concluded by reporting the following findings;

(i) The venting effect on both the flame propagation and explosion overpressure do not linearly increase with shortening the distance between the side vent and the ignition point. The venting effect of a side vent is not just influenced by the side venting position, but also significantly influenced by the inducement of an end vent.

(ii) A side vent exhibits opposite influences on the flame propagation before and after the flame passes the side venting position. As the flame propagates upstream a side vent, the flame propagation is mainly affected by an end vent, and little affected by the side vent. When the flame propagates downstream of the side venting position, the flame propagation is gradually decreased by the side venting effect.

(iii) For explosion overpressure, unlike with flame propagation, after a side vent is opened, the explosion overpressure can be obviously released by the side vent immediately, and the duration time of explosion overpressure is sensitive to the side venting position, but not in direct proportion with the peak overpressure, illustrating that the overpressure development affected by a side vent is influenced by both the side venting position and the interaction between the side vent and the end vent.

2.2.4 Bends

Explosions in pipes with a single bend, a U bend, or a Z bend are also quite different than explosions in straight pipes^[42, 43]. Understanding the influence bend pipes have on the flame behavior in gas explosions in industrial processes aids its prevention. Zhu et al.^[44], studied the flame acceleration in pipes containing bends of 3 different angles (including 52°, 90° and 145° as depicted in **Fig. 2-3**). They discovered the following:

(i) The flame acceleration in pipes with three different bend angles had a similar trend. The decreasing amplitudes in the 145°, 90° and 52° bends were 44.79%, 80.09% and 96.28%, respectively. The amplitude increased with a decrease in the bend angle.

(ii) The flame speeds were lowest in the 52° bend and greatest in the 145° bend. However, the maximum flame speeds in the pipe with the 52° bend were greatest and were lowest in that with the 145° bend. Both the flame speeds in bends and maximum flame speeds in the whole pipes increased as the bend position was moved further away from the ignition point.

Fig. 2-3 Pipes with three different bend angles. (a) 52°; (b) 90°; (c) 145°

2.2.5 Ignition Features

Influence of Ignition Position on Gas Explosion

Ignition position influences the explosion characteristics of flammable gases. In an experimental study of the influence of the ignition position within a cylindrical depressurization vessel upon the peak explosion overpressure, when a CH₄-O₂ mixture was ignited in the middle, Chao et al.^[45], observed a “double peak” phenomenon. The ignition position has a significant influence on a vented gas explosion in underground spaces, and the influence varies when presented with a small-scale or large-scale structure. The test tunnel is defined as small-scale when the volume is less than 17 m³, and as large-scale when the volume is larger than 17 m³. Recourt et al.^[21], Kasmani et al.^[46], reported that, a central ignition was observed to be the worst scenario for a vented gas explosion in a small-scale space. Kindracki et al.^[20], also conducted an experiment of a methane explosion in a closed horizontal pipe as depicted in **Fig. 2-4**, and found that a central ignition caused higher pressure in horizontal pipes.

Fig. 2-4 Schematic diagram of research tube: 1, ignition position: center; 2, ignition position: end or bottom; 3, ignition position: top^[20]

Influence of Ignition Position on Gas Explosion

Researchers have studied the effects of the initial ignition energy on the gas explosion and flame properties using both laboratory-sized and large-scaled explosion chambers^[47, 48]. Ajrash et al.^[49], investigated the effects of ignition energies on initiating a methane explosion. The results clearly indicated that (as presented in **Fig. 2-5**), the higher ignition energy sources can release higher temperatures, accelerate the methane oxidation process, and shorten the time for initiating the methane explosion.

Fig. 2-5 Initiation of methane ignitions by 1 kJ, 5 kJ, and 10 kJ ignition sources^[49]

2.2.6 Gas Composition and concentration

When the concentration of methane in the gas is between 8% and 10% the explosion intensity is the greatest^[50]. Wang et al.^[23] employed an experiment in a closed duct, and the highest flame speed was observed when the concentration of methane was close to the stoichiometric concentration. The flame velocity at a concentration of 10% reaches a maximum of 91 ms⁻¹ as presented in Fig. 2-6. The propagation trends of methane concentrations of 8% and 12% are similar to that of 10%, but their peak values are slightly lower. Furthermore, explosions may not be initiated if the gas concentration ranges out of the flammability limits^[17].

Fig. 2-6 Flame speed-time graph under different concentrations^[23]

2.2.7 Fuel Concentration

Fuel concentration has a significant effect on gas explosions. Gas explosions caused by fuel-air mixtures are likely to lead to catastrophic consequences in underground coal mines and tunnels. The consequences of a gas explosion are particularly dependent on the types of fuels and oxidizers and their concentrations^[17].

2.2.8 Influence of diameter on explosion flow field

As the diameter of pipeline increases (say across the range of 100-500 mm) the time required for combustion to complete increases. This is mainly because at larger diameters the Reynolds number of the gas is greater for a given velocity, which is advantageous to the combustion process as it increases the mixing of gases and therefore the reaction rate. However, for a larger diameter pipeline, more reactants are required which take longer to burn, extending the time required to complete combustion^[50].

3 Some Gas Explosion Remediation Approaches

3.1 Introduction

Considerable number of research have been conducted to develop formulations, devices, systems and influencing designs to achieve explosion suppression, explosion venting and explosion isolation to mitigate or suppress the propagation of gas explosions in pipeline (ducts). Most of the interventions deals with explosion suppressions. The suppression agents include inert gases, water mists, dry powders, and halogen compounds^[51]. The application of inert gases such as Argon (Ar) and Nitrogen (N₂) have been explored^[52, 53]. Mohammed et al.^[54], found that the addition of CO₂ has a much greater influence on the burning velocity and the temperature exponent compared to the addition of N₂. Water mist^[10], ultrafine water fog^[55] and water mist with additives (such as NaCl^[55], NaOH^[56], K₂CO₃^[57], NaHCO₃^[58]) have been tested for the mitigation of methane/air explosions. Explosion prevention has also been achieved by the use of porous solids placed within the pipe to extinguish the explosion flame under certain conditions^[59]. A significant number of research have discovered that the vent burst pressure, ignition position, and vent size have an important influence on flame propagation and pressure development in cylindrical vessels^[46, 60, 61]. Bao et al.^[62], investigated the influence of gas concentration and venting pressure on overpressure transients in the venting process of methane/air explosions in a 12 m³ concrete chamber. They also discussed the test generation conditions of four types of overpressure profiles with different overpressure transients. Considering a typical safety approach 3.2 will discuss the side vent effect on flame propagation deceleration and overpressure discharging in a duct.

3.2 Effect of side vent size on a methane/air explosion in an end-vented duct containing an obstacle

Wan et al.^[63], studied the influence of side vent size on the discharging effect; explosion characteristics including the visualization of flame propagation process, propagation velocity and overpressure on methane/air explosions in an end-vented duct containing an obstacle.

3.2.1 Experimental Apparatus and Method

Fig. 3-1 Experimental apparatus schematic of methane/air explosions affected by side venting in an end-vented duct containing an obstacle^[63]

Fig. 3-1 show the experimental system and components. The details of the experimental system and method are elaborated in^[63, 64].

3.3.2 Findings of the Experiment

(i) When a side vent with length of 60 mm is located in front of an obstacle, the existence of the obstacle will promote the flame to be released through the side vent. The vent will cause a better deceleration effect on flame propagation, and the time for the flame to propagate through the duct is much longer than that of the configuration without an obstacle. However, for a side vent with length of 100 mm, the discharging effect of the side vent itself is very strong, and the influence of the obstacle on flame propagation is relatively small.

(ii) The discharge effects of side vents with different vent sizes are obviously affected by the relative positions of the obstacle and the side vent. For a side vent in front of an obstacle, before the flame is encouraged by the obstacle, the explosion is effectively discharged by the side vent. Therefore, the side vent has a perfect effect on flame propagation deceleration and overpressure discharging, and the discharging effect is only slightly sensitive to the vent size. Whereas for a side vent behind an obstacle, when the flame arrives at the side vent position, the explosion intensity is very strong due to incentive effect of the obstacle. Accordingly, only a side vent with length of 100 mm has a considerable discharging effect, and the discharging effect is very sensitive to the vent size.

(iii) In practical applications, the side vent should be placed near the flammable point and set in front of potential obstacles to play an ideal role of safety relief.

3.3 Models

An endless list of models have been employed by researchers to study the characteristics and influencing factors of the propagation of gas explosion. Table 3-1 summarizes some of the models used in the study of the gas explosion propagation in pipelines (ducts).

Table 3-1 Some Models used in the study of the propagation of gas explosion in pipelines (ducts)

Model	Characteristic/Influencing factor investigated	Conclusions/finding
FLACS ^[16]	Characteristics of gas explosion in a natural gas compartment of urban utility tunnel	<p>Revealed that the flame profile undergoes two unstable flame stages.</p> <p>The length of the natural gas compartment and different ignition positions have slight effects on the maximum over-pressure.</p>
Numerical simulation ^[50]	<p>Characteristics of gas explosion flow fields in complex pipelines</p> <p>Several different diameters of straight pipes and a horizontal, bent pipe--analogous to that commonly used in Chinese coal mines--are selected as the focus of the research</p>	<p>Both in the straight and bending pipes, the pressure wave and velocity wave are accelerated by the rising of reaction rate.</p> <p>As the explosion progressed, with the temperature reaching approximately 3000 K, only one pressure wave and one reaction rate wave were observed, while several velocity waves were found.</p> <p>The larger diameter presented the highest relative pressure as well as the largest velocity increase and subsequent decrease inside the tube. The bent pipes caused both turbulence and kinetic energy to increase, resulting in the acceleration of the reaction rate. The burning time was 7.4% shorter than the burning time observed for the straight pipe.</p>
CAST model ^[65]	<p>Analyze the catastrophic underground pipeline gas explosion in Taiwan, which is one of the largest petroleum catastrophes in Chinese history.</p> <p>Hierarchically analyze</p>	<p>Systematically demonstrated the inadequate control and violated safety constraints and uncovered the in-depth rationale behind the decisions that were made leading up to this tragedy</p>

the safety control structure to enforce the safety constraints required by the system hazards

4 Conclusions

Various characteristic and influencing factors impact the propagation of gas explosion in pipelines (ducts). The following are some of the characteristics and influential factors that affect the propagation of gas explosion in pipeline (ducts). In triangular obstacles, the shear layer become prominent in the later stage of the explosion process and this contributes to enhancing the flame velocity and overpressure.

The flammability limit of mixtures is one of the important factors for preventing underground gas explosions. The gas cloud can be ignited and exploded once the LFL has been passed.

The venting effect on both the flame propagation and explosion overpressure do not linearly increase with shortening the distance between the side vent and the ignition point. The venting effect of a side vent is not just influenced by the side venting position, but also significantly influenced by the inducement of an end vent.

The ignition position has a significant influence on a vented gas explosion in underground spaces, and the influence varies when presented with a small-scale or large-scale structure.

When the concentration of methane in the gas is between 8% and 10% the explosion intensity is the greatest. Explosions may not be initiated if the gas concentration ranges out of the flammability limits.

Nomenclature

Abbreviation	Actual Meaning
CAST	Causal Analysis based on Systems Theory
FLACS	Flame Acceleration Simulation
DDT	Deflagration to Detonation Transition
LEL	Lower Explosion Limits
LFL	Lower Flammability Limits
UEL	Upper Explosion Limits
UFL	Upper Flammability Limits

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